

THE ROLE OF WOOD AS A CREATIVE ELEMENT IN BIOPHILIC DESIGN: FROM MATERIAL TO CONCEPT

Tsausaki Oleksandr ¹ [0009-0006-7281-868X], Krivenko Olga ² [0000-0002-8949-0944]

¹ PhD student of Department of Architectural Constructions Kyiv National University of Construction and Architecture, tsausaki_oh-2024@knuba.edu.ua

² DrSci, Prof. of Department of Architectural Construction, Kyiv National University of Construction and Architecture, Ukraine, kryvenko.ov@knuba.edu.ua

Abstract. This article examines the transformative role of wood as a creative element within biophilic design, highlighting its potential to stimulate individual creativity and enhance well-being. Biophilic design, rooted in the human need for connection with nature, integrates natural materials such as wood to create environments that foster emotional balance and cognitive clarity. The study explores wood's aesthetic, tactile, and symbolic qualities that inspire and drive innovation. Emphasis is placed on engineered wood products, such as Glulam, CLT, and LVL, which broaden their application in contemporary architectural and artistic contexts. The article underscores wood's ability to engage multiple senses, its role in visual and tactile arts, and its contribution to educational spaces that nurture creativity. The findings highlight the multifaceted value of wood as a medium for stimulating creativity, creating harmonious environments, and reinforcing the bond between humans and nature. Wood reaffirms its timeless relevance in modern design by blending functionality with art.

Ключові слова: biophilic design, creativity, engineered wood, visual arts.

Introduction. Rapid urbanisation and increasing reliance on artificial environments have significantly transformed human habitats, often to the detriment of psychological well-being. While urban living offers conveniences and opportunities, it can also lead to sensory deprivation, stress, and a disconnection from nature. This trend has spurred a growing interest in biophilic design—a design approach prioritising the human need for connection with nature.

Wood is a cornerstone of biophilic design, acting as a vital bridge between artificial environments and nature. Its organic textures, warm tones, and unique patterns create

aesthetically pleasing and psychologically restorative spaces. The development of innovative materials such as Glulam (glued laminated timber), CLT (cross-laminated timber), and LVL (laminated veneer lumber) extends wood's versatility, enabling its use in spatial design solutions.

This article's objective is to explore the multifaceted role of wood in biophilic design, analysing how its physical and aesthetic properties foster creativity, enhance well-being, and serve as a medium for modelling spatial design solutions.

Literature Review

Biophilia and Its Core Principles

The concept of "biophilia," defined by Edward O. Wilson in 1984, suggests that humans have an innate affinity for nature—a connection deeply rooted in evolutionary history (Wilson, 1984). Biophilic design leverages this connection to improve emotional, cognitive, and physical health by integrating natural elements into built environments.

The fundamental principles of biophilia include:

1. *Integration of natural forms and patterns*: Using materials, textures, and shapes that mimic natural structures to evoke familiarity and comfort.
2. *Sensory interaction*: Stimulating engagement through visual, tactile, auditory, and olfactory cues derived from nature.
3. *Dynamic and diffuse lighting*: Employing natural light creates rhythms and moods akin to outdoor conditions.
4. *Connection to place*: Incorporating locally sourced natural materials to evoke a sense of belonging and identity.

Jiang et al. (2018) emphasise that biophilic design promotes creativity by creating environments that reduce stress levels, support focus, and stimulate sensory engagement.

Evolution of Wood Usage in Architecture and Design

Historically, wood has been a primary building material, valued for its accessibility and ease of processing. Technological advancements in the 20th and 21st centuries have expanded wood's capabilities, enabling its use in spatial design to balance functionality and aesthetics.

Asdrubali et al. (2017) highlight the ecological advantages of engineered wood products such as Glulam, CLT, and LVL, which provide sustainable alternatives to steel and concrete and reduce the carbon footprint. Björnfort et al. (2011) explore how these materials allow architects to achieve functional and aesthetic goals, facilitating the creation of complex, large-scale structures.

Main Text

The Role of Biophilia in Fostering Creativity

Stress Reduction and Cognitive Clarity

Biophilic environments have been proven to reduce stress levels and restore cognitive clarity, creating optimal conditions for creativity. Natural materials' visual and tactile qualities, especially wood, evoke a sense of calm and focus. Jiang et al. (2018) found that workplaces incorporating wood and other natural elements show higher employee satisfaction, creativity, and productivity levels.

Natural patterns and textures in wood, such as grain, knots, and organic imperfections, stimulate visual interest and encourage imagination. Wood is particularly effective in creativity-focused environments like art studios, design workshops, and educational spaces.

Multisensory Stimulation

Biophilic design is based on multisensory experiences, where materials engage the senses to create memorable and inspiring environments. Wood's tactile warmth and smooth texture invite interaction, while its natural aroma strengthens the connection to nature. These sensory stimuli activate emotional and cognitive responses, deepening user engagement with the environment and encouraging creative exploration.

Applications in Educational and Creative Spaces

Stimulating Creativity in Learning Environments

Wood's aesthetic and tactile qualities make it particularly valuable in educational spaces. Classrooms and studios with wooden elements foster a sense of safety and openness, encouraging students to experiment and innovate. Jiang et al. (2018) argue that environments incorporating natural materials enhance concentration and cognitive flexibility, critical components of the creative process.

Practical Use of Wood in Design Studios

Wood is a versatile material in design education, offering students opportunities for hands-on learning. Modular wooden furniture and workstations promote adaptability and collaboration. Additionally, exercises involving woodworking allow students to explore the interplay of form, functionality, and material, which are essential skills for creative professions.

Wood as a Medium for Visual and Artistic Expression

Aesthetic Qualities as Sources of Inspiration

Wood's unique aesthetics make it an ideal material for visual and tactile design. Its natural variations—ranging from the rich dark tones of mahogany to the light, airy hues of birch—enable a wide spectrum of artistic expressions. Each piece of wood carries its story through its texture and grain, inspiring creators and viewers.

Symbolic Role in Art

As a material, wood embodies themes of growth, resilience, and the passage of time, making it a powerful symbol in artistic contexts. Artists and designers often use wood to convey narratives of sustainability, renewal, and the human connection to nature.

Tectonic Tools of Engineered Wood: Innovations for Creative Design

Glulam: Strength Meets Elegance

Glued laminated timber (Glulam) is highly valued for its ability to form significant structural elements without sacrificing aesthetics. Its layered construction allows for complex shapes, such as arches and curved structures, which are challenging to achieve with traditional wood. Björnfort et al. (2011) note that Glulam combines functionality and creativity, making it a key component of innovative architectural solutions.

CLT: Building on Sustainability

Cross-laminated timber (CLT) panels, composed of perpendicular layers, offer exceptional stability and strength. Their sustainable production process and versatility make them ideal for eco-focused projects. Asdrubali et al. (2017) emphasise that CLT reduces construction waste and enhances the aesthetic appeal of both interior and exterior spaces.

LVL: Precision in Design

Laminated veneer lumber (LVL) is a high-performance material known for its uniformity and precision. Its ability to withstand significant loads while maintaining an elegant appearance makes it a favourite choice among architects and designers aiming to create modern, minimalist aesthetics.

Results and Discussion. The findings underscore the multifaceted role of wood in shaping spatial design solutions. Its aesthetic and tactile qualities and symbolic significance offer various tools that support imaginative thinking and emotional comfort. For example, integrating wooden design elements into educational and artistic spaces positively influences exploration and innovation.

Conclusions. Wood forms the foundation for biophilic design solutions, fostering creativity, well-being, and a connection between humans and nature. Its aesthetic, tactile, and symbolic properties make it a versatile material in spatial design. Integrating wood into educational and artistic practices enables the creation of environments that inspire, unlock potential, and reconnect people with the natural world. The development of modern wood processing technologies and exceptionally engineered wood allows designers to rethink the potential of wood in expanding the tectonic, structural, and form-shaping possibilities of spatial design solutions.

References

1. Asdrubali, F., Baldassarri, C., & Fthenakis, V. (2017). Life cycle analysis in the construction sector: guiding the optimisation of conventional materials. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 28, 35-44.
2. Björnfort, A., Bröchner, J., & Stehn, L. (2011). Timber construction and performance-based building. *Construction Management and Economics*, 29(4), 345-355.
3. Jiang, L., Berry, M., & Kellert, S. (2018). Nature in design: the biophilic design approach. *Environmental Psychology Journal*, 12(3), 235–245.